

CON-TEXTOS KANTIANOS.
International Journal of Philosophy
N.º 5, Junio 2017, pp. 344-345
ISSN: 2386-7655
Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.805975

**A Discussion Around Katrin Flikschuh's: *Kant's Nomads:
Encountering Strangers***

***Una discusión sobre Los nómadas de Kant:
encontrando extraños***

JOËL MADORE*

Memorial University, Canada

For the past four years now, Memorial University has hosted workshops exploring specific themes in the philosophy of Immanuel Kant. They have been organized on the basis of a more intimate format: Kantian scholars from around the world present their current research on the given topic of the workshop, followed by individual responses from Faculty members and a subsequent question period. In addition, these talks are complemented by graduate panels whose presentations are inspired by their own thesis work. The aim of this focused approach is to encourage a closer, more detailed attention to current trends in Kantian Studies. These workshops have so far examined ongoing investigations on faith, education and the Enlightenment.

The latest event was held on the question of hospitality in Kant, with Dr. Katrin Flikschuh (London School of Economics) presenting a paper entitled: “Kant’s Nomads: Encountering Strangers”. The text itself is part of a larger project on Kantian cosmopolitanism, tentatively entitled, *What is Orientation in Global Thinking – A Kantian Inquiry*, to be published at Cambridge University Press. It is an engaging and thought-provoking piece, meant to assess how Kant, and his readers alongside, can re-orient their

* Professor of Philosophy at Memorial University, Canada. Email contact: joel.madore@mun.ca.

thinking following their encounter with societies who do not share Europe's political framework. The paper left a deep impression on the philosophical community at Memorial University, who turned out in large numbers to listen and react to Dr. Flikschuh's argument. The following dossier proposes to retrace this discussion, if only partially. The author's article is obviously at its center, followed by three responses from Faculty members. It is a deeply engaging debate for all those concerned with the challenges of pluralist societies, Kant's duty of hospitality, cultural diversity, and the encounter with the unknown.

